

RIGHTS, RACE AND MOBILITY

NATURALISED CHINESE IN THE AUSTRALASIAN COLONIES

KATE BAGNALL 白碧

UNIVERSITY OF TASMANIA

M. 1658

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION.

WHEREAS *Ah Dong*
now of *Moorina* in the Colony of Tasmania,
Miner an Alien by birth, did on the
Fourth day of *October 1892*, present

Chinese Southern
Diaspora Studies

Volume 8, 2009

南方華裔研究雜誌

第八卷, 2019

New Perspectives in
Chinese-Australian
History and Heritage

In memory of
Dr Barry McGowan OAM
(1945–2018)

[http://chl.anu.edu.au/chinese-southern-diaspora-studies/
chinese-southern-diaspora-studies-volume-eight-2019](http://chl.anu.edu.au/chinese-southern-diaspora-studies/chinese-southern-diaspora-studies-volume-eight-2019)

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ASTORIA.

GOLDEN WEDDINGS

BAGNALL—BELLAMY.—April 11, 1895, at St. Clement's Church, Marrickville, by Canon Bellingham. Henry Baskerville Bagnall, of Dudley, England, to Florence Bellamy, of Dunedin, New Zealand. Present address, 42 Hardy Street, Hurlstone Park.

SNEDDON—PAUL.—April 11, 1895, by the late Rev. Peter McQueen, Thomas, youngest son of the late John and Mary Sneddon, to Julia Elizabeth, second daughter of the late Charles and Elizabeth Paul. Present address: Afton-Ayr, 4 Silsoe Street, Hamilton, Newcastle, N.S.W.

QUONG TART, League of Wheelman Starter, with
MR. BAGNALL.

Margaret Tart, *The Life of Quong Tart ; or,
how a foreigner succeeded in a British
community*, W.M. Maclardy, Sydney, 1911

I'm
Timothy Fay Loie.
I was naturalised in
New Zealand in
1906.

I'm
Sin Quan Loie.
I arrived in
New Zealand in
1904.

We are Dora,
Hannah and David
Fay Loie.
We were born in New
Zealand and are British
subjects by birth.

LINKING LEGISLATION + LIVES

'Chinese Republicans', *Sunday Times*, 12 August 1923, p. 13, <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article120532459>

No. XIII.

An Act to Naturalize Timothy Goodwin Pitman. PITMAN'S NATURALI-
ZATION.
[5th July, 1825.]

WHEREAS Timothy Goodwin Pitman a citizen of the United Preamble.
States of America hath been for some time resident in the
Colony of New South Wales and is desirous of settling therein And
whereas it is expedient that certain of the advantages and privileges
which are enjoyed by His Majesty's natural-born subjects should be
extended to him the said Timothy Goodwin Pitman Be it therefore
enacted by His Excellency the Governor of New South Wales with Oaths to be taken
and declaration sub-
scribed as directed
by the 1 Geo. 1.
the advice of the Council that when and so soon as the said Timothy
Goodwin

MEMORIAL, OR APPLICATION FOR A CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION.

77/3730
20 May

To His Excellency Sir Charles Augustus Fitz Roy, Knight Companion of the Royal Hanoverian Guelphic Order, Governor General of all Her Majesty's Australian Possessions, and Captain General and Governor-in-Chief of the Territory of New South Wales and its Dependencies, &c., &c., &c.

1.—The Memorial of *Ralph Ah How* of *Jembaicumbene (Bdwt)* respectfully sheweth that your Memorialist is a native of* *Canton*

2.—That your Memorialist is *34* years of age, and is† *a Store Keeper*

3.—That your Memorialist arrived in the Colony of New South Wales, by the ship *_____* in the year *1857* and has been resident therein since that date.

4.—That your Memorialist begs to refer your Excellency to the annexed Certificate of character and of the correctness of the statements herein contained from respectable persons to whom your Memorialist has been known since his‡ arrival in the Colony.¶

5.—That your Memorialist§ *is desirous of purchasing land in New South Wales*

; and that on these grounds your Memorialist is desirous of availing himself|| of the privileges granted to Aliens by the Acts of Council, 14 Victoria, No. 39, and 17 Victoria, No. 8.

6.—That your Memorialist therefore respectfully requests that your Excellency may be pleased to grant to your Memorialist a Certificate under the provision of the said Act, conferring upon your Memorialist the privileges of a natural born British Subject, with such restrictions as to your Excellency may seem meet.

And your Petitioner will ever pray.

Signature *Ralph Ah How*

Date *April 25th 1872*

We, the undersigned, do hereby certify as to the correctness of the statements contained in the subjoined Memorial, that we have known the Memorialist¶

for upwards of six years, and believe him to be a person of respectable character.

R. W. Hensley
St. James

at 20 May 1872
certificates taken with
our signatures
letters
20 May 1872

- * Insert District or Town, and Country.
- † Profession, Trade, or Calling.
- ‡ Or her
- § Here state the grounds on which the Certificate is desired.
- || Or herself.
- ¶ From his arrival in the Colony, or from the (specify date.)

Name: Ralph Ah How

Place of residence: Jembaicumbene

Age: 34 years

Occupation: Storekeeper

Duration of residency: Since 1857
(15 years)

Grounds on which certificate desired:
Desirous of purchasing land in NSW

Date of application: 25 April 1872

* Insert District or Town, and Country.
 † Profession, Trade, or Calling.
 ‡ Or her
 § Here state the grounds on which the Certificate is desired.
 || Or herself.
 ¶ From his arrival in the Colony, or from the (specify date.)

FIRST COLONIAL ALIENS / NATURALISATION LEGISLATION

South Australia 1846

New South Wales 1849

Tasmania 1861

Queensland 1861

Victoria 1863

New Zealand 1866

Western Australia 1871

FIRST COMMONWEALTH / DOMINION ALIENS / NATURALISATION LEGISLATION

Australia

Naturalization Act 1903

New Zealand

Aliens Act 1908

I'm
Matilda Lo Keong
from Dunedin.
I arrived in
New Zealand
in c.1874 from
Victoria.

I'm
Lo Keong from
Dunedin.
I was naturalised
in 1882.

@baibi

CHINESE POPULATION

	NSW	Victoria	Tasmania	NZ
1861	12,988	24,732		
1871	7,220	17,826		
1881	10,205	11,959	844	5,004
1891	13,157	8,489	939	4,444
1901	10,222	6,347	506	2,936

NEW SOUTH WALES LEGISLATION: CHINESE IMMIGRATION & NATURALISATION

Chinese Immigrants Regulation and
Restriction Act 1861

Prohibited Chinese naturalisation

Chinese Immigration Act Repeal Act 1867

*Removed prohibition on Chinese
naturalisation*

Influx of Chinese Restriction Act 1881

Chinese Restriction and Regulation Act
1888

Prohibited Chinese naturalisation

Immigration Restriction Act 1898

Immigration Restriction Act 1901 (Cwth)

Naturalisation Act 1903 (Cwth)

*Prohibited naturalisation of 'Aboriginal
natives of Asia'*

CHINESE IMMIGRANTS REGULATION AND RESTRICTION ACT OF 1861 (25 VIC NO 4)

- entry by sea limited to one Chinese for every 100 tons of shipping
- £10 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- receipt certificates issued to Chinese who paid the poll tax
- exemption certificates issued to Chinese already resident in NSW
- **naturalisation of Chinese prohibited**
- repealed in 1867

I'm
William Chi from
Scone, NSW.
I was naturalised
in 1868.

Hannah Maria (nee Mason) and William Chi with their baby, c. 1867
Courtesy Elaine Hetherington

INFLUX OF CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1881 (45 VIC NO 11)

- £10 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 100 tons of shipping
- Chinese = 'any person of the Chinese race'
- **exemptions for British subjects**
- bona fides residents of NSW could apply for exemption certificates

CHINESE RESTRICTION AND REGULATION ACT OF 1888 (52 VIC NO 4)

- £100 poll tax on Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one for every 300 tons of shipping
- exemptions for:
 - British subjects by birth
 - Chinese naturalised in NSW
 - Chinese who held exemption certificates under 1881 Act
- **naturalisation of Chinese prohibited**

No. 46 *64604/3942*
BA 7010

CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1888.

Name Willie Yuen
Occupation Storekeeper
Place of Birth Canton
Nationality Chinese
Date of arrival in New South Wales Year 1878
Passenger by ship Bowen
Age 39 years — months. in 1900
Height 5 feet 2 3/4 inches. in 1900
If naturalized in N.S.W., date
of naturalization N^o 355, 28th November 1883.

Signature Willie Yuen

Remarks Issued for the purposes of identification to Willie Yuen and attached to Certificate of Naturalization N^o 355 28th Nov 1883.
Has a scar on forehead just over left eyebrow.

J. H. D. Mohr
Collector of Customs.

Custom House at Sydney
19th Janry. 1900

33799

NEW SOUTH WALES	Prohibited by law between 1862 and 1867, and after 1888	Chinese prohibited from naturalisation under Chinese restriction legislation, 1861 and 1888
VICTORIA	No certificates granted after 1887	
SOUTH AUSTRALIA	No certificates granted after 1887	
WESTERN AUSTRALIA	No certificates granted after 1891	
QUEENSLAND	Certificates granted up to 1903	Anti-Chinese provision in Aliens Act 1867 – must have lived in colony 3 years, must be married with wife also resident in colony
TASMANIA	Certificates granted up to 1903	
NEW ZEALAND	Certificates granted up to 1907	

CHINESE NATURALISED IN COLONIAL NSW 1856-1888

EXEMPTIONS FOR BRITISH SUBJECTS

	New South Wales	Victoria	Tasmania	New Zealand
1881	£10 poll tax 1 Chinese for 100 tons shipping	£10 poll tax 1 Chinese for 100 tons shipping		£10 poll tax 1 Chinese for 100 tons shipping
	Exemption for British subjects Exemption certificates for NSW residents	Exemption for British subjects		Exemption certificates for NZ residents
1887 1888	£100 poll tax 1 Chinese for 300 tons shipping	1 Chinese for 500 tons shipping	£10 poll tax 1 Chinese for 100 tons shipping	£10 poll tax 1 Chinese for 100 tons shipping
	Exemptions for: – British subjects by birth – Chinese naturalised in NSW – Chinese who held exemption certificates under 1881 Act	Exemption for Chinese naturalised in Victoria Special exemptions issued by proclamation of the Governor	Exemptions for: – bona fide residents of Tasmania – British subjects	Exemption for Chinese naturalised in NZ
	Naturalisation of Chinese prohibited			

NATURALISATION
CERTIFICATE

COLONIAL BORDER

NATURALIZED BUT NOT NATURALS.

THE use of being poll taxed
Our Mongols fail to see;
So they get made into Britishers,
And cut about scot free.

'Naturalized But Not Naturals,'
Melbourne Punch, 18 October 1883, p. 1,
<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article174560576>

CHINESE ARRIVING IN SYDNEY, 1888–1894

@baibi

Sailed by vessel in which they arrived	14,197
Sailed for China	4,354
Sailed for Melbourne	669
Sailed for New Zealand	299
Sailed for Tasmania	175
Sailed for Queensland	124
Died in port	5
Remaining in port on 31 May 1894	51
Landed at Sydney	181
– British born	4
– Exemption papers	7
– Paid poll tax	15
– Naturalisation papers	155
Total	20,055

NATURALISATION LEGISLATION IN NEW ZEALAND

Naturalization Acts,
1845–1866

Aliens Act
1866, 1870, 1880, 1908

Naturalization Act
1870 Fees Act, 1871

Aliens Act
Amendment Act,
1882, 1892

Aliens Act 1866 stipulated
application fee of £1

Aliens Act Amendment Act 1882
reduced application fee to
2 shillings & sixpence, except for
Chinese

Aliens Act Amendment Act 1892
abolished application fee, except for
Chinese

**No Chinese
naturalised from
1908 to 1951**

Cabinet decision
of
4 February 1908
to decline
naturalisation
applications of
Chinese due to
'risk of immigration
fraud'

CHINESE NATURALISATION IN AUSTRALIA TO 1904

Victoria	2969
New South Wales	908
Tasmania	592
South Australia & Northern Territory	284
Queensland	110
Western Australia	22
Total	4,885

FIRST NATURALISED CHINESE IN NEW ZEALAND

1. Appo Hocton, a cattle breeder from Nelson, on 25 August 1852
2. John A Tong, a cabinetmaker from Wellington, on 16 May 1866

New Zealand.

ANNO TRICESIMO

VICTORIÆ REGINÆ.
No. 61.

ANALYSIS.

- Title. 1. Short Title.
Preamble. 2. Persons named in Schedules A. and B. naturalized.

AN ACT for the Naturalization of certain persons in the Colony of New Zealand.
[8th October 1866.]

WHEREAS by an Act of the General Assembly of New Zealand intituled "The Naturalization Act 1865" it was amongst other things enacted that every person who should be declared to come within the operation of the said Act by any proclamation to be issued in that behalf by the Governor should from the time in such proclamation specified be deemed and taken until the termination of the then next session of the General Assembly to be and to have been from such specified time a natural-born subject of Her Majesty within the said Colony And whereas the persons particularly described in the Schedule A. hereunto annexed have from time to time been so declared to come within the operation of the said Act and the persons particularly described in the Schedule marked B. hereunto annexed have settled in the said Colony and are desirous of being declared to be natural-born subjects of Her Majesty within the said Colony and it is expedient that there should be removed from all such persons as aforesaid within the said Colony the disabilities to which aliens are by law subjected

BE IT THEREFORE ENACTED by the General Assembly of New Zealand in Parliament assembled and by the authority of the same as follows—

- I. The Short Title of this Act shall be "The Naturalization Act 1866."
II. The persons who are particularly described in the Schedules A. and B. to this Act annexed shall to all intents and purposes whatsoever within the said Colony be deemed and taken to be and to have been from the dates set opposite their respective names natural-born subjects of Her Majesty as if they had been respectively born within the realm of England.

SCHEDULE A.

Date of Proclamation.	Name.	Native of	Occupation.	Residence.	Date from when to take effect.
13 Nov., 1865	Frederick Kropp	Schmolsin, Prussia	Carpenter	Dunedin	1 Jan., 1863
Ditto	Franz Gottfried Hermann Kummer	Mecklenburg Stralitz, Germany	Clerk	Wellington	1 Nov., 1865
5 Dec., 1865	Dominic Galosi	Marches, Italy	R.C. Priest	Auckland	14 Nov., 1865
Ditto	Joseph Gregori	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Nivard Jourdan	Piedmont, Italy	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Francis Del Monte	Bologna, Italy	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Stephen Passinetti	Lombardy, Italy	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Bendix Hallenstein	Brunswick, Germany	Merchant	Queenstown, Otago	15 Feb., 1862

Supplement to the New Zealand Gazette No. 47, of 17th August, 1866.

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Naturalization.

SCHEDULE A.—continued.

Date of Proclamation.	Name.	Native of	Occupation.	Residence.	Date from when to take effect.
5 Dec. 1865	Edward Dow	Maine, U.S. America	Farmer	Collingwood, Nelson	13 Nov., 1865
6 April, 1866	Christian Emil Peterson	Schleswig-Holstein, Germany	Hotel-keeper	Dunedin	5 Oct., 1862
Ditto	Hermann Luks	Oldenberg, Grmy.	ditto	Waikouaiti, Otago	1 Aug., 1863
Ditto	Bernard Luks	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Christian C. Blucher	Magdeburg, Prussian Germany	Licensed Surveyor	Auckland	1 Jan., 1865
Ditto	Doretta Blucher	ditto	Wife of the above	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Edmund Blucher	ditto	Child of the above	ditto	ditto
Ditto	William Blucher	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Gustave Blucher	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Rudolph Platow	Pillau, Prussia	Miner	Arrow River, Otago	12 Jan., 1866
Ditto	Leopold Lessong	Hesse Electoral, Germany	Surveyor	Auckland	13 Jan., 1866
Ditto	Samuel Goldston	Poland	Storekeeper	Arrow Town, Otago	15 Feb., 1866
Ditto	George Sutter	Canton of Grieson, Switzerland	Miner	ditto	6 Feb., 1866
Ditto	Marco Spongia	Italy	Master Mariner	Lyttelton	20 Feb., 1866
Ditto	John Charles Miller	Apenrade, Denmk.	Settler	Hooper's Inlet, Otago	1 Oct., 1860
Ditto	Raffaele Auriemma	Naples	ditto	Wellington	1 Jan., 1864
Ditto	William Spiering	Bergedorf, Hamburg, Germany	Tailor	Auckland	1 Jan., 1866
18 May, 1866	Horatio Sebastian Hatfield	New York	Boatman	Wellington	1 Jan., 1860
Ditto	Daniel Quadri	Switzerland	Publican	Hokitika, Canterbury	16 Oct., 1865
Ditto	Hermann Colm	Prussia	Merchant	Christchurch	31 Oct., 1865
Ditto	Leopold Dentice	Italy	Tailor	ditto	1 Jan., 1860
Ditto	Henry Hofmeister	Germany	Shoemaker	ditto	1 May, 1863
Ditto	Johann Mehrtens	ditto	Farmer	Lincoln Road, Canterbury	1 Jan., 1862
Ditto	Johann Viebroch	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Heinrich Rattigen	ditto	ditto	ditto	1 Jan., 1862
Ditto	Lauretz Neilson	Denmark	Labourer	Porter's Pass, ditto	1 Jan., 1864
Ditto	Marcus Sandstein	Austria	Jeweller	Christchurch	1 Dec., 1862
Ditto	Alexander Quelde	Warsaw, Poland	Baker	Coromandel, Auckland	1 Jan., 1866
Ditto	Joseph Jennings	Portugal	Settler	Opotiki, Auckland	21 Mar., 1866
Ditto	Bernard Folckman	Saxony	Cabinet-maker	Nelson	3 April, 1866
Ditto	Gustave Hirsch	Baden, Germany	Dyer	Dunedin	27 April, 1866
Ditto	John Bartlett Green	U.S. America	Bushman and Overseer	ditto	27 Mar., 1866
Ditto	John Grenfield	Terschelling, Kingdom of Holland	Boatman	Oamaru, Otago	8 Mar., 1866
Ditto	Francis Richard Claude	Chili	Settler	Auckland	7 Mar., 1866
Ditto	John Charles Frederick Meyer	Hamburg, Grmy.	Storekeeper	Laurance, Otago	1 Feb., 1862
Ditto	Samuel Felpe	Warsaw, Poland	ditto	Wetherston, Otago	1 Dec., 1861
Ditto	John Nelson	Haperanda, Swdn.	Butcher	Havelock, Marlborough	1 Jan., 1864
Ditto	Andrew Peten	Denmark	Hotel and Store-	Lower Taieri Ferry, Otago	26 Feb., 1866
Ditto	John A. Tong	Canton, China	Cabinet-maker	Wellington	15 May, 1866
13 July, 1866	Elizabeth Fosbinder	Prussia	Settler	Gladstone, near Invercargill	1 July, 1862
Ditto	Elizabeth Tabeling	ditto	ditto	ditto	ditto
Ditto	Bernhard Ekensteen	Sweden	Merchant	Invercargill	1 April, 1863
Ditto	Nathan Goldwater	Kollo, Rus. Poland	Storekeeper	Auckland	1 Dec., 1857
Ditto	Philippe Aimé Martin	France	R.C. Priest	Arrowtown, Otago	29 May, 1866
Ditto	Francis Malcon	Austria	Settler	Wellington	1 Jan., 1866

SCHEDULE B.

Name.	Native of	Occupation.	Residence.	Date from when to take effect.
David Louis Rod	Switzerland	Miller	Waimea South, Nelson	19 Feb., 1866
William Homes	Denmark	Farmer	Blenheim, Marlborough	1 Jan., 1857
Francis Schringe	Italy	Sailor	Ferry Road, Christchurch	Jan., 1860
Julius Mendelson	Russian Poland	Storekeeper	Timaru	1 Aug., 1865
Herman Nashelski	Poland	Ironmonger	Christchurch	Jan., 1862
Solomon Nashelski	Poland	Ironmonger	Christchurch	Jan., 1862
Manheim Krakout	Posen, Prussia	Storekeeper	Hampden, Otago	1 Aug., 1866
John Borgfeldt	Germany	Farmer	Papanui	1 Jan., 1857
Joso Garcia	Preo, Azores	Mariner	Akaroa	24 Sept., 1866

WELLINGTON, NEW ZEALAND:

Printed under the authority of the New Zealand Government by GEORGE DIDSBUY, Government Printer.

FIRST NATURALISED CHINESE IN VICTORIA

Chow Ga Hon (趙宜端)

Lain Anding (林亞亭)

Wang Ah Hae (黃亞喜)

All carpenters living in
Melbourne

Naturalised in December 1854

1854
J. His Excellency Sir Charles Hotham Knight
Lieutenant Governor of the Colony of
Victoria and its Dependencies
The Memorial of Wang Ah Hae of
Little Bourke Street in the City of
Melbourne in the Colony of Victoria (Carpenter)
Respectfully sheweth

That your Memorialist is a native
of Canton in China
That your Memorialist is thirty five
years of age and is by trade a Carpenter
and Joiner

That your Memorialist arrived in
the Colony of Victoria by the Ship "Christian"
in the year one thousand eight hundred and forty
three and has been resident therein since that date

That your Memorialist begs to refer
your Excellency to the annexed Certificate of
Character and of the correctness of the statements
therein contained from respectable persons to whom
your Memorialist has been known since his
arrival in the Colony

That your Memorialist intends to
settle and reside in this Colony and carry on
his business therein and on these grounds your
Memorialist is desirous of availing himself
of the privileges granted to aliens by the Act
of Council 10th Victoria Number thirty nine

That your Memorialist therefore respectfully
requests that your Excellency may be pleased
to grant to your Memorialist a Certificate under
the provisions of the said Act conferring upon
your Memorialist the privileges of a native
born British subject with such restrictions as
to your Excellency may seem meet

And your Petitioner will ever pray
Dated this fifteenth day of December 1854.

黃亞喜

CERTIFICATE TO NATURALIZE, UNDER THE PROVISIONS OF THE ACTS
OF THE GOVERNOR AND COUNCIL, XI VICTORIA, No. 39, AND
XVII VICTORIA, No. 8.

Yan Sout

WHEREAS, in accordance with the provisions of an Act of the Governor and Legislative Council of New South Wales, passed in the Eleventh year of the Reign of Her Majesty Queen Victoria, intituled, "An Act to amend the laws relating to Aliens within the Colony of New South Wales," and of another Act of the said Governor and Legislative Council, passed in the Seventeenth Year of the Reign of Her said Majesty, intituled, "An Act to amend an Act relating to the naturalization of Aliens,"

Yan Sout has presented to me a Memorial in the form and manner prescribed by the said first recited Act, praying that he may be naturalized; And Whereas, I have enquired into the truth of the circumstances set forth in the said Memorial, I the Governor aforesaid, do hereby Certify that it has been established to my satisfaction that *Yan Sout* is a native of *Amoy* is *thirty two* years of age, and that having arrived by the *Ship* in *the Year 1852* he is now residing in *Grafton* and is desirous of settling in the *Glory* having purchased land in the Township of *Grafton*

he desires to obtain the advantages of the said Act; and I do therefore grant to the said *Yan Sout* (upon his taking before one of the Judges of the Supreme Court, or before a Police Magistrate, or Bench of Magistrates in Petty Sessions assembled, or before a Person deputed by a Judge of the Court for the purpose, the Oath prescribed by the said first recited Act,) all the rights and capacities within the said Colony of New South Wales, of a natural born British Subject, except the capacity of being a Member of either the Executive Council, Legislative Council, or Legislative Assembly.

GIVEN under my Hand and Seal at Government House, Sydney, in New South Wales aforesaid, this *Eleventh* day of *September* One thousand eight hundred and *fifty seven*.

L.S. (Signed) *W. Denison*

BY HIS EXCELLENCY'S COMMAND,

(Signed) *Charles Cooper*

ENTERED on Record by me, this *fourteenth* day of *September* One thousand eight hundred and *fifty seven*

W. Cooper
for the COLONIAL SECRETARY AND REGISTRAR.

FIRST NATURALISED
CHINESE IN
NEW SOUTH WALES

Yan Sout of Grafton

Native of Amoy

32 years old

Naturalised in September 1857

FIRST NATURALISED CHINESE IN TASMANIA

Quong Kee:

Cabinetmaker, Launceston

William A'Ching:

Cabinetmaker, Launceston

Yeen Lock:

Tin miner, Thomas' Plains

Naturalised on 21 June 1882

NATURALISATION RECORDS

- **New South Wales colonial:** State Archives NSW, Sydney
- **Victoria colonial:** National Archives of Australia, Canberra
- **Tasmania colonial:** Tasmanian Archives, Hobart
- **New Zealand:** Archives NZ, Wellington
- **Australia (federal from 1904):** National Archives of Australia, various offices

Some indexes and records are available through [ancestry.com](https://www.ancestry.com)

QUITE AN ACQUISITION.—Jamie Chow Yee, cook, of Lawrence, is gazetted a full-blown British subject.

Southland Times, 19 June 1884

84/1114

To His Excellency the Governor of New Zealand.

Name. THE Memorial of Samie Chow Yee
Residence. Chinese Camp, Lawrence, (Cook's) in the Colony of New Zealand,
Occupation. Cook made in conformity with the provisions
of "The Aliens Act, 1880."

Humbly sheweth,—

Name. 1. That the name of your Memorialist is Samie Chow Yee
Age. 2. That your Memorialist is Forty one years of age.
Birthplace. 3. That your Memorialist was born at Canton in China
Residence. 4. That your Memorialist resides in Chinese Camp, Lawrence
Length of residence, and desire to settle. 5. That your Memorialist has been residing in the Colony in New Zealand for
Thirteen years, and is desirous of settling therein.

Prayer. And your Memorialist prays that Letters of Naturalisation may be granted
to him.

Signature of Memorialist: Samie Chow Yee

DECLARATION OF VERIFICATION.

I, Samie Chow Yee, the above-named memorialist,
do solemnly and sincerely declare that all the above-stated facts relating to myself
are true as I have stated them; and I make this solemn declaration conscientiously
believing the same to be true, and by virtue of an Act of the General Assembly
of New Zealand intituled "The Justices of the Peace Act, 1866."

Declared at Lawrence Samie Chow Yee
this 20 day of March 1884
before me—Amos Auld J.P.

(Jonas Harrop)

I, the undersigned Amos Auld
do hereby certify that I know Samie Chow Yee
the Memorialist named in the foregoing Memorial, and that, to the best of my
knowledge and belief, he is a person of good repute.

Place: Lawrence Amos Auld J.P.
Date: 20th March 1884

JAMIE CHOW YEE

- Naturalised 6 June 1884
- Age 41
- Cook
- Born in Canton
- Lived at the Chinese Camp, Lawrence
- 13 years in New Zealand

JAMIE CHOW YEE

- Memorial completed and signed by Justice of the Peace (Jonas Harrop): 20 March 1884
- Memorial sent by solicitor (John Copland) to Colonial Secretary: 21 March 1884
- Oath of allegiance sworn and signed before JP (Jonas Harrop): 16 May 1884
- Oath of allegiance and stamp for £1 sent by solicitor (John Copland) to the Colonial Secretary: 26 May 1884
- Letters signed by Governor: 6 June 1884

ELECTORAL ROLL, TUAPEKA, 1896

499	Chase, James Edward, Tuapeka Mouth, miner, residential
500	Chew Lain, Sam, Tuapeka Flat, hotelkeeper, freehold, sec. 20, block 20, Tuapeka East
501	Chew Lain, Amelia, Tuapeka Flat, domestic duties, residential
502	Childs, Edward Harry, Earnscliffe, laborer, residential
503	Chisholm, Hugh, Alexandra South, constable, residential
504	Chisholm, Harriet Ann, Alexandra South, domestic duties, residential
505	Chisholm, Alexander, Galloway Station, shepherd, residential
506	Chitty, George, Roxburgh, coachman, residential
507	Chitty, Euphemia, Roxburgh, wife, residential
508	Chow Tie, Grace, Tuapeka Flat, wife, residential
509	Chow Tie, Tuapeka Flat, butcher, residential
510	Chow Yie, Jimmy, Tuapeka Flat, cook, residential
511	Chong, Thomas Chee, Roxburgh, miner, residential
512	Christian, Charles, Waipori, miner, residential
513	Christie, Honor Martin, Blue Spur, housekeeper, residential
514	Christie, John Wilson, Blue Spur, miner, residential

CHINESE NATURALISATIONS IN NEW ZEALAND TO 1907

TOTAL = 498

PLACE OF BIRTH OF NATURALISED CHINESE IN NZ

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**PLACE OF
RESIDENCE OF
NATURALISED
CHINESE IN NZ**

N = 94

(AT TIME OF
APPLICATION)

Number

1. Wellington
2. Dunedin
3. Auckland
4. Palmerston North
5. Kumara

**PLACE OF
RESIDENCE OF
NATURALISED
CHINESE IN NZ**

N = 94

(AT TIME OF
APPLICATION)

PLACE OF RESIDENCE OF NATURALISED CHINESE IN NZ (AT TIME OF APPLICATION) TOP 25 PLACES TOTAL = 94

OCCUPATIONS OF NATURALISED CHINESE IN NZ (AT TIME OF APPLICATION)

N = 45

STATED REASONS FOR NATURALISATION IN NSW

Purchase of land

Business or trade in the colony

Settled in the colony

Married or family in the colony

Become a Christian

Wishes to vote in elections

Rights of ingress and egress

'Why Chinese wish to become British subjects passed my understanding ... I cannot for the life of me see where they are to benefit by becoming British subjects while they are held in contempt by the people who grant them the privilege. I see no objection whatever to their becoming naturalised British subjects providing that they are placed on an equality with other British subjects. Otherwise the arrangement is one-sided.'

Hwang Yung-Liang 黃榮良
Chinese Consul for New Zealand

Southland Times, 8 April 1909

THE END OF COLONIAL CHINESE NATURALISATION

New South Wales None between 1862 and 1867, and after 1888

Victoria None after 1887

South Australia None after 1887

Western Australia None after 1891

Queensland Granted until 1 January 1904

Tasmania Granted until 1 January 1904

New Zealand Granted until 1907

I'm
Charles Wong Hee
from Mathinna,
Tasmania.
I was naturalised in
1902.

I'm
Tutoy Chinn. I was
born in Weldborough,
Tasmania.
My father, Maa Mon
Chinn, was naturalised
in 1882.

COMMONWEALTH OF AUSTRALIA

STATUTORY DECLARATION

Referred to in Paragraph 1 of annexed Application.

1. Name in full. (Write clearly)

I, John Broshang

do solemnly and sincerely declare that—

1. My name is

John Broshang

2. My place of residence is at

Adaminaly

in the State of

Western Australia

3. My occupation is

storekeeper

in which capacity

I am at present and have been employed by

2. Name and address of employer.

for a period of

4. I was born on the

29th day of November

year 1883, at

Hong Kong

in the

in the country of

China

5. My nationality is

Chinese

The nationality of my father was

Chinese

His full name was

Du. Broshang

The nationality of my mother prior to her marriage was

Chinese

6. I arrived in Australia from

Hong Kong

on the

day & month uncertain

in the year

1852

per the

not known

and disembarked at the

port of

Sydney

7. State places and periods in each.

7. Since my arrival in Australia I have resided at

Sydney 2 years Melbourne 1 year
Maitland 3 years Rialdia 8 years. Roma 4 years Adaminaly 50 years.

8. I have not been away from the Commonwealth of Australia at any time during the last twelve months.

9. After leaving the country of

and before

coming to Australia, I resided in the following countries for the periods stated

8. State each country and period in each.

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9. State whether married or unmarried, and if married full name, age, and residence of wife.

10. I am

married

My wife's full name is

Anastasia Gracey Broshang

She was born at

Adaminaly

Her age is

59

years. She resides at

Adaminaly

10. State number.

11. I have eight children. Their names, ages, birthplaces, and

residence are as follow:

Pauline	47	Adaminaly	now residing at - Waratah St. - Adelaide
Alice	38	"	"
Ada	36	"	"
Thomas	35	"	"
John	27	"	"
William	25	"	"
Walter	23	"	"

12. I have not been naturalized in any other country.

(NOTE.—If the Applicant has been naturalized in any other country this statement should be amended accordingly, and particulars of such naturalization furnished.)

11. State town and State.

13. I was registered as an alien in

(Certificate No.)

12. State name of country.

14. I intend to settle permanently in Australia

13. The country of which applicant is a subject at the time of making his declaration.

15. I have not obtained or applied for permission from the Government of China to retain my nationality as a subject of that country. I do not intend to apply for such permission, and I shall not avail myself of any such permission should it be granted to me by any law of China

And I make this solemn declaration by virtue of the Statutory Declarations Act 1911, conscientiously believing the statements contained therein to be true in every particular.

Declared at Adaminaly

the Twenty fourth

day of January 1923

John Broshang

Before me, George Goodman J.P.

It is particularly requested that the writing, especially of the names of persons and places, be plain and legible.

NOTE.—Any person who wilfully makes a false statement in a Statutory Declaration is guilty of an indictable offence, and is liable to imprisonment with or without hard labour for four years.

@baibi

KATE BAGNALL

SENIOR LECTURER IN HUMANITIES
UNIVERSITY OF TASMANIA

kate.bagnall@utas.edu.au
www.chineseaustralia.org

M. 1658

CERTIFICATE OF NATURALIZATION.

WHEREAS *Ah Dong*
now of *Moorina* in the Colony of Tasmania,
Miner an Alien by birth, did on the
fourth day of *October 1892*, present
to me a Memorial praying me to grant unto him the said *Ah Dong*

I'm
Quong Tart
from Sydney, NSW.
I was naturalised
in 1871.

